

Original Article

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**PREVALENCE OF DIABETIC
KETOACIDOSIS AMONG THE PATIENTS
PRESENTING IN THE EMERGENCY
DEPARTMENT**

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ABSTRACT:

Diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA) is a potentially life-threatening complication of diabetes mellitus. Signs and symptoms may include vomiting, abdominal pain, deep gasping breathing, increased urination, weakness, confusion and occasionally loss of consciousness. This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in the emergency department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender and diagnosis of diabetic ketoacidosis after blood sugar and urinary ketones were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. A total of 200 patients presenting in the outdoor department were included in this study i.e., 100 males (50%) and 100 females (50%). The mean age of the patients was 36.45±4.12 years. Only in two patients, diagnosis of diabetic ketoacidosis was made.

Keyword: Diabetic Ketoacidosis

INTRODUCTION:

Diabetic ketoacidosis (DKA) is a potentially life-threatening complication of diabetes mellitus. Signs and symptoms may include vomiting, abdominal pain, deep gasping breathing, increased urination, weakness, confusion and occasionally loss of consciousness. A person's breath may develop a specific "fruity" smell. Onset of symptoms is usually rapid. People without a previous diagnosis of diabetes may develop DKA as the first obvious symptom. DKA happens most often in those with type 1 diabetes but can also occur in those with other types of diabetes under certain circumstances. Triggers may include infection, not taking insulin correctly, stroke and certain medications such as steroids. DKA results from a shortage of insulin; in response, the body switches to burning fatty acids, which produces acidic ketone bodies. DKA is typically diagnosed when testing finds high blood sugar, low blood pH and ketoacids in either the blood or urine.

The primary treatment of DKA is with intravenous fluids and insulin. Depending on the severity, insulin may be given intravenously or by injection under the skin. Usually, potassium is also needed to prevent the development of low blood potassium. Throughout treatment, blood sugar and potassium levels should be regularly checked. Antibiotics may be required in those with an underlying infection. In those with severely low blood pH, sodium bicarbonate may be given; however, its use is of unclear benefit and typically not recommended. Rates of DKA vary around the world. In the United Kingdom, about 4% of people with type 1 diabetes develop DKA each year, while in Malaysia the condition affects about 25% of type 1 diabetics a year. DKA was first described in 1886 and, until the introduction of insulin therapy in the 1920s, it was almost universally fatal. The risk of death with adequate and timely treatment is around 1–4% (1-3).

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in the emergency department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender and

diagnosis of diabetic ketoacidosis after blood sugar and urinary ketones were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

A total of 200 patients presenting in the emergency department were included in this study i.e., 100 males (50%) and 100 females (50%). The mean age of the patients was 36.45 ± 4.12 years. Only in two patients, diagnosis of diabetic ketoacidosis was made.

DISCUSSION:

Diabetic ketoacidosis may be diagnosed when the combination of hyperglycemia (high blood sugars), ketones in the blood or on urinalysis and acidosis are demonstrated. In about 10% of cases the blood sugar is not significantly elevated ("euglycemic diabetic ketoacidosis"). A pH measurement is usually performed to detect acidosis either on blood from a vein or artery. Subsequent venous pH measurements (to ensure treatment is effective), may also be taken from a vein, as there is little difference between the arterial and the venous pH. Ketones can be measured in the urine (acetoacetate) and blood (β -hydroxybutyrate). When compared with urine acetoacetate testing, capillary blood β -hydroxybutyrate determination can reduce the need for admission, shorten the duration of hospital admission and potentially reduce the costs of hospital care. At very high levels, capillary blood ketone measurement becomes imprecise.

In addition to the above, blood samples are usually taken to measure urea and creatinine (measures of kidney function, which may be impaired in DKA as a result of dehydration) and electrolytes. Furthermore, markers of infection (complete blood count, C-reactive protein) and acute pancreatitis (amylase and lipase) may be measured. Given the need to exclude infection, chest

radiography and urinalysis are usually performed. If cerebral edema is suspected because of confusion, recurrent vomiting or other symptoms, computed tomography may be performed to assess its severity and to exclude other causes such as stroke. Diabetic ketoacidosis is distinguished from other diabetic emergencies by the presence of large amounts of ketones in blood and urine, and marked metabolic acidosis. Hyperosmolar hyperglycemic state (HHS, sometimes labeled "hyperosmolar non-ketotic state" or HONK) is much more common in type 2 diabetes and features increased plasma osmolarity (above 320 mosm/kg) due to profound dehydration and concentration of the blood; mild acidosis and ketonemia may occur in this state, but not to the extent observed in DKA. There is a degree of overlap between DKA and HHS, as in DKA the osmolarity may also be increased. Ketoacidosis is not always the result of diabetes. It may also result from alcohol excess and from starvation; in both states the glucose level is normal or low. Metabolic acidosis may occur in people with diabetes for other reasons, such as poisoning with ethylene glycol or paraldehyde (4-6).

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